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Abstract

This deliverable is three folded. It addresses the objective of “Reflecting on current challenges of social data collection” associated with the tasks on:

T2.3 Debate and reflect on the future ethical issues concerning GDPR and Migration

T2.4 Debate and reflect on the future ethical issues concerning Administrative data linkage

T2.5 Debate and reflect on the future ethical issues concerning Access to data

The reporting on GDPR and Migration and on Administrative data linkage reflections and feedback from Young people are intended to be published as a research output, while the text on Access to data is to be used as a a blogpost with hyperlinks added.

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1 GDPR and Migration

Moving on Ethics: mobility, humanism and research participation

Introduction

Migration between countries is a complex phenomenon that can have significant implications for individual migrants and the societies that they move to. Within the European Union (EU) the free movement of people makes migration between countries much more straightforward than for countries outside the EU. Nevertheless, at the individual level significant barriers remain for individuals who migrate. Difficulties in adjusting to a new culture, language, and moving away from family and friends can have serious implications for the well-being of individual migrants. Indeed, this might be especially true for children who often feel they lack agency when families decide to migrate (Moskal and Tyrrell, 2015). Free movement within the EU has also led to significant problems within European countries. Large scale movement between countries has also created social tensions at times. Indeed, high levels of immigration from other European countries is thought to have been a factor in the decision of the UK to leave the EU (Arnorsson and Zoega, 2018).

It is therefore essential to better understand the impact that migration can have on children, young people, and their families. The Growing Up In Digital Europe (GUIDE) project offers an opportunity to do so. As the first cross-country cohort study of child wellbeing it is theoretically possible for the study to track participants across countries if they, or their families, migrate within Europe. This has rarely been possible before. However, important barriers to doing so exist in terms of the ethical questions that such tracking would entail and rules governing data under GDPR.

This report summarizes the current thinking concerning the ways in which ethical issues related to data collection are dealt with in the social sciences. It discusses contemporary issues such as migration and relates these to the responsibilities that researchers have to study participants, especially when they are children. It also discusses how researchers can build relationships of trust with research subjects and highlights that positive researcher-participant relationships might be a way to avoid attrition. It then discusses the results of a Youth Advisory Board (YAB) in which young people were asked about what they thought about these issues before concluding. Prior to doing this it first discusses the general position that researchers take in terms of conducting ethical research in the social sciences and especially for sociological research involving children and migrants.

In disciplines such as Sociology, History, Psychology or Anthropology, deontological guidelines or ethical codes are usually produced by the researchers and/or the communities involved.¹ They involve

¹ For example: The Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), *Framework for Research Ethics*; American Sociological Association (ASA), *Code of Ethics*; British Psychological Society (BPS), *Code of Conduct, Ethical Principles, and Guidelines*; Social Research Association (SRA), *Ethical Guidelines*; British Sociological Association (BSA), *Statement of Ethical Practice*.

epistemological, situational, and relational issues and debates. Among those is the (re)negotiating entrée, the development of boundaries, the issue of reciprocity, consent, transparency, and the requisites of confidentiality and anonymity. However, these issues are often considered cross-cutting aspects of research projects, and do not stand as an independent discussion. Research funders and ethics committees handle ethics differently, taking a more legalistic, bureaucratic, universalistic, standardized approach. These include checklists and requirements consisting of consent forms, confidentiality, safety procedures, anonymization processes, collection and storage of data, privacy, and data digital storage compliance issues. A set of ethical requirements concerning authorship credit, plagiarism, deception and concealment of information, and other examples of ethical misconduct are also frequently presented in these types of guideline. This check-list style approach relates to accountability in scientific research, since there is clearly a “greater concern among representatives of universities, research funding bodies, and professional associations to exhibit good ethical credentials” (Bryman, 2012: 131). To these aspects there are still others to be added when outside the social sciences, within the medical, and biological sciences.

In addition to this more general and principle-based approach to ethics, on one hand, and to the more practical and check-list like approach, on the other, there is an important set of ethical issues that should be taken into account in any research involving individuals:

- Discipline and Territorial anchors: This concerns the disciplinary and national diversity of the deontological codes of the researchers and the territory in question. In Sociology these affect factors such as power dynamics and bias in interviews, fieldwork and surveys, reflexivity, feminist and indigenous methods, or community-based research (van de Scott, 2020). In Anthropology about it is closely related to the tensions between ethnography and advocacy, the overemphasis on unique local moral and ethical assemblages, the need and feasibility to have a prior informed consent in written form, and the mosaic of potential collaborative research projects (Brightman and Grotti, 2020).

- Positionality towards the subject under investigation: This concerns the research participants and the research context and process. The individual’s world view; values and beliefs that are shaped by their political allegiance, religious faith, gender, sexuality, historical and geographical location, ethnicity, race, social class, and status, (dis)abilities and so on; the position the researchers adopt in face of a research task and its social and political context (Foote and Bartell 2011, Savin-Baden and Major, 2013 and Rowe, 2014 in Holmes, 2020). This is intimately related to reflexivity as in “the politics of positionality”, about acknowledging our power, privileges, and biases throughout the research process (Madison, 2005, p. 6 in Leavy, 2020). It requires “sensitivity to the cultural, political, and social context of the researcher” (Bryman, 2012) and researched. This is especially the case when dealing with people from a migrant background. It also requires sensitivity to the age position of the researcher if the research subjects are young.

- Translation and ideology: In fact, “the ideology of a translation resides not simply in the text translated, but in the voicing and stance of the translator” (Munday, 2007), which may affect the way different children and young people are questioned in different settings.

- Power theories and relations, such as feminist theories, post-colonial theories and Marxist theories, which can influence every step of the way in a research process. In a survey these theories can

determine who to include, what questions to ask, how to ask them, and what response options to offer, and are all a result of an explicit or implicit theoretical approach. Feminist theory has criticized the abstract interpretation and commitment to ethical principles, proposing instead an ethics of care, that “gives central concern to the interdependence of human beings and their responsibilities to each other” (Hammersley and Traianou, 2011).

There are different paradigms co-existing well, but not quite communicating or bridging, as is the goal of our article (figure 1). On one hand is a situational ethics, where decisions on how to ethically conduct research have to be considered on a case-by-case basis. Authors that defend a “principled relativism” (Fletcher, 1966), argue that the breaking of some alleged ethical rules to begin with, is what has allowed social scientists to learn about phenomena and realities that would otherwise be inaccessible to them. We can apply this relativism not with a strict instrumental purpose, but with a humanist purpose. Moreover, “situation” does not have to be understood as the interaction taking place during interviews, but as the long-term interaction that takes place between researchers and participants in a longitudinal survey. Attrition studies show us, for example, that participants are lost in socially unequal fashion. That is, attrition occurs at a higher rate for the more socially disadvantaged. In most cases, losing one participant should be a reason of concern. Not (just) for the feasibility and sustainability of the survey, but for the “other” person.

Figure 1. Ethical paradigms and practices

Ethics: The impact of the General Data Protection Regulation

The most important recent European legislation impacting ethical research debates is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Although it regulates only a specific part of the larger area of ethical

issues – data protection - it illustrates well this universalistic, morality-promoting, potentially inflexible ethical paradigm, however well-intentioned with the privacy and agency of the individuals. It is, however, data-centred and not human-centred.

The GDPR came into effect in the European Union (EU) in 2018 and led to significant changes in individuals' rights concerning their data. This binding legislative instrument aims to promote free movement of personal data and to preserve the rights and freedoms of individuals inside the EU (regardless of citizenship) in terms of the right to privacy and data protection (EDPB, 2019; Rudusans and Vitols, 2021; Vukovic *et al.*, 2022). The European Parliament shifted from the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC to a Regulation which is legally enforceable by EU Member States. The right that everyone has to freely control his or her personal data is protected by the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (article 8). Breaches in complying to data protection laws are considered a criminal offense and subject to sanctions (Clarke, *et al.*, 2019; Supervisor, 2020; Boudjaaba, 2021).

This reshaped commitment towards data protection binds both public and private organizations, universities and research institutions and mirrors the effort to create a wider space for data protection law harmonisation (Shawn, 2017). Despite this approach, the Regulation allows EU Member States to decide how to implement it and gives some margin of manoeuvre to decide about key aspects such as the age to give consent.

The GDPR tackles one main concept which is central to data protection: the concept of personal data. The Regulation provides a definition: “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person” (article 4 (1)). On top of this, there are special categories such as sensitive personal data (article 9 (1)) which involve data concerning ethnicity, sexual orientation, or religious beliefs. This adds an extra layer of complexity and concern. In order to mitigate the risks of identifying data subjects when collecting, processing, and storing their data, anonymization techniques should be applied. Organizations must take measures which guarantee that a correspondence between a person and her or his personal data is not possible. When a data subject is not identifiable, GDPR ceases to apply: data is no longer personal data (Avraam *et al.*, 2018; Mourby *et al.*, 2018).

Importantly GDPR allows for personal data to be shared between countries (article 1 (3)). This would allow research teams to transfer the personal contact information to those in other countries when a research participant migrates. In practice consent to do so would be sought from participants before any migration.

Research, as a key producer of scientific knowledge, is considered by the GDPR to be a public good which “can provide the basis for the formulation and implementation of knowledge-based policy, [and] improve the quality of life for a number of people” (recital 157) and therefore must be supported. Furthermore, according to GDPR (article 6 (4); recital 50), organizations processing personal data for scientific, historical, or statistical purposes may avoid restrictions on secondary data and sensitive categories of data processing, provided that they implement the appropriate safeguards (article 89) for the rights and freedoms of data subjects (the research participants). This approach to research, indicates that the Regulation does not see a conflict between scientific research and individuals rights thus allowing for some adaptation in what concerns data protection laws (EDPB, 2019; SRA, 2020; Foxhall, 2020).

Indeed, research is shielded within the GDPR (the “research exemption”) to the point that data processing institutions may override the right of a data subject to object to processing or to request the erasure of personal data (article 17 (3) (d)) if such actions undermine the research purposes. Further, data processing organizations are given the possibility to retain personal data for longer periods, overlapping the principle of storage limitation. So, the general rules have exceptions. These occur when it comes to greater good such as *research results* and *funding*, or *scientific contributions* in general. There appears to be no exemptions or exceptions, however, when it comes to greater good at the *individual level*, following an individual request or silent cry for help.

In order to balance these exceptions, the Regulation asks for appropriate safeguards that abide by the principles of purpose and proportionality (EDPB, 2019; SRA, 2020). The GDPR recommendations to researchers are both ethical and practical. Procedures concerning personal data must occur in a lawfully, fairly, and transparent manner, have specific and limited purposes, use anonymisation or pseudonymising where possible, ensure that only minimal data is collected and stored in accurate terms for no longer than necessary. Where data minimization is concerned, researchers are advised to collect only what they “need-to-have instead of (...) collecting data that is nice-to-have”, as Crutzen *et al.* (2019), put it. Research organizations are accountable for complying with these guidelines as well as keeping the integrity and security of data (Crutzen, Peters and Mondschein, 2019; SRA, 2020; Quinn, 2021; Ivankovic *et al.*, 2022).

According to GDPR (article 6), researchers must define purpose and an appropriate lawful basis for data processing activities (task of public interest, legitimate interest, or rightful consent). Consent stems out of a trustful research relation. It is mandatory that it includes clear and unambiguous information, enough for a freely and voluntarily engagement. It should be as easy to withdraw consent as it was to give it (Mourby, Gowans, Aidinlis, Smith, & Kaye, 2019; Mulder & Tudorica, 2019; Boudjaaba, 2021; Klykken, 2022).

The GDPR enforcement was greeted with apprehension and some controversy (Mourby, et al., 2018; Quinn, 2021; Vukovic *et al.* 2022). The principle of accountability combined with the sanctioning regime proposed by the GDPR in case of non-compliance with the data protection laws (fines and bans on processing data); consent as a lawful basis for processing personal data being threatened by the right to withdraw; the GDPR research derogations that may be limited by requirements like necessity, proportionality and by privacy rights and the apparent paradox between GDPR compliance and open science, are among the issues raised by the research community (Vestoso, 2018; Clarke *et al.*, 2019; Foxhall, 2020). Regulations such as this, have created, in some territories, an environment of control and mistrust, that is unhealthy to the development of science.

“They believe their work is being constrained and distorted by regulators of ethical practice who do not necessarily understand social science research. In the United States, Canada, United Kingdom, New Zealand and Australian researchers have argued that regulators are acting on the basis of biomedically driven arrangements that make little or no sense to social scientists. How did we reach this point? How is it that social scientists have found themselves caught between their clear commitment to ethical conduct and unsympathetic regulatory regimes with which they are expected to comply? Why is there such antagonism between researchers who believe they are behaving ethically and regulators who appear to suggest they are not?” (Israel and Hay, 2014).

According to Vukovic *et al.* (2022) the Regulation is being interpreted differently throughout EU Member States and institutions within them. Unclear understanding can lead to GDPR over-interpretation and pose barriers to research.

In spite of the possible hurdles, compliance to GDPR should not feel like “a millstone around the researcher’s neck” (Crutzen, Peter and Mondschein, 2019: 1350). The requirement for data minimisation, for instance, can function as a means to improve focus and efficiency of the research and in addition can lighten the participants’ burden and prevent dropouts. Making data open is possible from the moment that data is anonymised and thus GDPR does not apply as it is no longer personal data. In the case of longitudinal studies, researchers have to link through an identifier, different datasets, where the “research code” proposed by Peters (2018) can be used (Crutzen, Peter and Mondschein, 2019). Nonetheless, to advise in data processing and to handle possible data breaches, researchers should involve a Data Protection Officer (Comission, 2018). This figure is variably specialized in each country and institution.

Research that recognizes and nourishes scientific knowledge as a co-constructed product within a collaborative relationship, is also responsive to participants’ agency and life dynamics and provides for ongoing negotiation and continuous consent (Klykken, 2022). Putting participants’ wellbeing first, providing a respectful space for their participation whether in case of consent or in case of refusal, and to nurture a “shared affinity” (Flinders, 1992 quoted by Klykken, 2022: 107) contribute to trustfully shape the research relationship, one where the participants feel they are listened to and remain attuned with the research purposes (Foxhall, 2020; Gans-Combe, 2022). Above all, complying with the GDPR requirements is taking into consideration the participants’ fundamental rights and protecting their personal data. It is, nonetheless, important to have in mind that protecting the data and ensuring privacy of the individual at all costs, is not the only way, and can even be the opposite, of protecting the human rights and wellbeing of the individual. In research, as in life, we should treat the other as someone deserving of being seen, heard and remembered.

Ethics that move through time and space: migration, mobility, and longitudinal research

Longitudinal Research is about collecting data, characteristics of human lives, across time. Longitudinal data seeks to find the changeability, correlation and the association between potentially time-varying variables. In the case of the GUIDE survey², this search is motivated by the need to address the multidimensionality and temporal changes in wellbeing for children and young people. As wellbeing is

² “GUIDE (Growing Up In Digital Europe: EuroCohort) will be Europe’s first comparative birth cohort survey: a Research Infrastructure that will be an important source of high quality longitudinal statistical evidence to support the development of social policies which will enhance the wellbeing of children, young people and their families across Europe for many years to come. GUIDE/EuroCohort will be an accelerated cohort survey including a sample of new born infants as well as a sample of school age children. Both cohorts will be surveyed using a common questionnaire and data collection methodology at regular intervals until the age of 24 years” (official site at: <https://www.guidecohort.eu>).

the focus of GUIDE the inclusion of populations and individuals is an ethical responsibility of upmost importance. Children and young people, on one hand, who might be migrants and refugees, on the other, as potentially vulnerable people, increase both the importance and the ethical and empirical complexity of their inclusion in a longitudinal survey. After all, researchers should “push against forces that seek to dehumanize, generalize, and altogether minimize “other” people”, and researchers must be fully committed to an inquiry stance that critically examine[s] every facet of research” (Ravitch and Carl, 2016: 317).

Migrants and mobile citizens, with variable levels of vulnerability, need to be included into longitudinal surveys. Not only to be able to assess the impact of mobility in the social trajectory of wellbeing, but also as a research stance: longitudinal statistical inclusion is an act of care, one that humanizes “the unit of analysis” and can contribute to the protection of the human rights. Being out of our sight does not mean being invalid for our observation. The rise in migration and mobility flows, increased by “the great disrupter” of Covid-19, the war in Ukraine, and the increased concerns about “peace and security as drivers of stability, development and safe migration” in the Mediterranean, as well as the impacts of climate change, and the human rights problem of human trafficking (Macauliffe, Triandafyllidou, 2022) should be taken into account when trying to develop an inclusive and humanist survey. Indeed, each of these factors will continue to be drivers of migration into the future, within and beyond Europe.

Good practices are, in this regard, of the essence. As in other mobilities, it is definitely possible to address them with both eyes open (Thomson, 2004), as well as ears wide open, to welcome the opinions and advice of young people themselves.

Vulnerability and Responsibility

The concept of vulnerability was first introduced in research ethics’ lexica in the Belmont Report in 1979 (Bracken-Roche *et al.*, 2017). Although commonly accepted that there are research participants that are “more likely to be mistreated, abused, exploited or harmed” (Malgieri and Jedrzej, 2020) there has been some debate around the boundaries and meaning of vulnerability, and what constitutes vulnerable groups.

According to the International Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical Research Involving Human Subjects (Sciences, 2002, guideline 13), “vulnerable persons are those who are relatively (or absolutely) incapable of protecting their own interests. More specifically, they may have insufficient power, intelligence, education, resources, strength, or other needed attributes to protect their own interests.”. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the European Commission Data Protection Impact Assessment guidelines, acknowledge the vulnerable as persons who may have limited capacity to make voluntary and informed decisions, to provide consent or object to their personal data processing. They are also those who might suffer from a power imbalance relationship between the data controller and themselves (Levine *et al.*, 2004). The GDPR considers people vulnerable because of their circumstances: minors, the elderly, people with disabilities and mental disorders or ethnic minorities, migrants, among others.

Although in literature, the concepts of vulnerability or vulnerable people may slightly differ, the common denominator is that they are people for whom researchers should implement special safeguards. The researchers must be aware and responsive towards any level of vulnerability found in participants or communities. First of all, purpose limitation is required. Is it completely necessary to

involve vulnerable participants? If so, the researchers have the obligation and responsibility (Malgieri and Jedrzej, 2020) to guarantee that the people involved will not “be stigmatised, retraumatised or otherwise harmed” (Comission, 2021) by participating in the research.

In parallel with the focus on protecting individuals’ free will, through informed consent, there are some challenging stances. Critics argue that labeling persons or groups as vulnerable also creates space for stereotypes that can be harmful (Levine *et al.*, 2004). Others think that the empahis on vulnerability translates into a “distrust of participants’ capacities” (Klykken, 2022). Schulz (2021) points to the assymetrical understanding of the research relationship: the reseachers as experts versus the presumed vulnerable informants. This paternalistic stance fails to recognize the participants’ potential “multiple and fluid positionalities” (Schulz, 2021: 552) and consolidates a knowledge imbalance in research relationships.

Apart from researchers and research participants having different views about vulnerability depending on the place they live, the political or religious framing or the social norms that they abide to (Loue and Loff, 2013), we argue that these different approaches can only be reconciled by an informed, situated and careful ethical practice. This approach is not accessible only by checking all the guidelines’ boxes before entering the field, hence the need for a context-oriented approach which can equip research of “response-ability” (Beach and Eriksson, 2010: 131).

Good practices of surveying across time

Following this we can consider some of the better practices that have been developed over the years when conducting longitudinal research involving children. In terms of the discussion above, young children are potentially ‘vulnerable’ insofar as they are unable to provide consent for the data collection themselves and are therefore reliant on parents or carers to exercise responsibility in understanding the risks involved in enrolling them in a research study. This is complicated further when the research study in question is longitudinal, where children and young people will be repeatedly surveyed over a number of years. In the case of a birth cohort, study children will commonly be enrolled into the study as infants and might be followed and re-surveyed for the rest of their lives. For example, in the National Child Development Study (NCDS), in the UK, infants and their families were first surveyed in 1958. There have been 11 follow up surveys since this initial survey with the most recent occurring in 2020 when participants where aged around 62.

A number of points can be made: when the members of the NCDS were first surveyed they were obviously unable to provide consent themselves. Rather parents or carers had to provide this. However, as cohort members have moved through the study they became, at some point, able to provide informed consent. A second important point for our purposes concerns the fact that as individuals move over time many will also necessarily move between places. This is one of the key sources of attrition in a longitudinal survey, particularly one that takes place over many years. As well as raising concern from the perspective of consent, long-term cohort studies are also at risk of changing practices and laws around the ethical handling of respondent data. For example, even relatively recent studies, such as the Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) from 2000, have had to adapt to changes in legislation such as GDPR. Therefore, for reasons of both consent and the fact that the basis for consent will be subject to change over time it is good practice to ask respondents to complete a consent form at each wave of the survey.

Research should be based on the informed consent of research subjects, prior to which the participants have been provided with adequate information on what the participation in the research includes, the possible limits to their participation, and any potential risks participation in the study may incur (Sin, 2005). Researchers should also be aware of the type of consents required for large scale longitudinal surveys. The most typical forms of informed consent in longitudinal research are active and passive consent. In active consent the subject is given a specific statement to agree on participating the study (or, in case of minors, their child participating the study), and they show their consent by "actively" agreeing. In passive consent the subject is first informed about the research and then assumed to have consented to participating unless he/she explicitly states otherwise. Research institutions also have regulations and ethical guidelines concerning the form of informed consent. Sometimes ethical guidelines of the institution where the study is conducted might change, which may further influence the need for consents, their form, and who is able to provide it (e.g., young people themselves or their parents). For example, until recently the ethical board of the University of Helsinki, Finland required active consent for participation from parents of 15-year old adolescents and under. However, the current guidelines state that in case of large-scale surveys (N>400) passive consent from the parents is enough for 15-year olds and above to participate.

In large scale longitudinal surveys following participants across decades, it might be challenging to predict all the ethical considerations which may take place decades later. Therefore, a good practice is to place longitudinal surveys as subject to regular review in order to ensure that appropriate ethical controls are in place and contemporary preferences are accounted for (Lynn, 2009). For example, over time general views and ethical considerations may change concerning sensitive topics, such as asking about participants' gender identity, ethnicity, and country of origin, and related questions will need to be updated. Recently it has become a norm to include 'other' as a response option under gender (female, male) questions in surveys whereas decade ago it was less common.

Migration is an important factor in a cohort study. The first kind of migration is inwards migration into the study country. This can be dealt with by incorporating migrants into the original sample. If this is not possible, or if it is felt that the inclusion of migrants in the sample becomes important during the course of the study, this can be done at a later date by including people from a migrant background in later waves of the study. For example, the sample size of NCDS increased between the first and fourth waves as migrants born in 1958 were added to the sample (Plewis et al., 2004). The second type of migration arises as individuals themselves move within the study country, and potentially migrate out of it. The former is a problem which can be resolved by establishing a means to communicate with people independently of where they live. The second problem is more difficult and has traditionally been dealt with by treating emigration as a form of attrition and allowing participants to re-enter the study if they return to the study country.

In the context of a cross-national cohort study, it becomes theoretically possible to follow individuals as they move between countries within the scope of the study. Few studies have attempted to do this. Nevertheless, it might be plausible that over the course of a multi-decade study that people moving within Europe might increase to relatively high levels where it becomes important to consider the impact of migration on research participants. Given GDPR has been adopted across Europe it is possible that researchers would be able to seek the consent of participants to pass on their information to survey

teams based elsewhere to maintain continuity of participation in the survey. However, the risks of doing so are currently underexplored given the increased risks of identifiability that might arise.

In terms of within country migration a number of good practices have been developed over the years that would be applicable to studies that wish to follow people between countries. A particularly important set of studies are those conducted by the Centre for Longitudinal Studies in the UK who are responsible for the NCDS, British Cohort Study 1970 (BCS), the Millennium Cohort Study 2000 (MCS), and Next Steps. A range of methods have been adopted which allow participating families to be tracked, and if necessary, traced when they move home. In a cohort profile of the MCS (see Connelly and Platt, 2014) they note that contact details are sought annually, and that families who move without supplying contact information are tracked using administrative records, as well as through 'stable contacts' that have been previously provided. If an interviewer finds that a household has moved they will make an effort to identify the new address of the respondent by contacting the new occupier, neighbours, local estate agents and other sources. Such approaches have proven to be an effective way keeping attrition as low as possible (Calderwood, 2010). The feasibility of implementing these methods in the case of cross-national migration should be explored further.

These activities are not without problems however, and it has been argued that if researchers wish to undertake tracing activities then it may be necessary to gain consent to do so (Lessof, 2009). Obviously, such consent must necessarily be gained prior to the respondent moving at an earlier wave of the study. The act of tracing a respondent should not raise ethical concerns on behalf of respondents. This is likely to be a particularly important concern for surveys dealing with young people, who will eventually move out of their childhood home and are more likely to move countries, but who should have the opportunity to remain in a study if they wish to do so.

Longitudinal studies, and in particular those which focus on children will encounter a range of ethical issues. These range from the age at which children and young people are able to provide meaningful consent, to the problems of attrition, particularly among vulnerable groups. As will be discussed below attrition, and the concern that it may render a study increasingly unrepresentative, may itself pose difficult ethical issues for researchers and interesting questions might be raised about the responsibility that researchers have to respondents in ensuring that a study remains viable. The difficulties of following participants across time and between countries is a problem for prospective cohort studies. However, a number of approaches exist that might allow researchers to maintain participation in the study. Indeed, it is argued that given this should be possible under GDPR and the provision to allow the free movement of personal data. Respondents should be given the opportunity to remain in a study even if they move country. This will provide scientific benefits as tracking individuals as they move between countries has rarely been done, and it will also allow participants to be in control of whether or not they remain in a study.

Moving on ethics: right to be forgotten vs. right to be remembered

The right to be forgotten appears in the Article 17 of the GDPR. It states that:

“The data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of personal data concerning him or her without undue delay and the controller shall have the obligation to erase personal data without undue delay.”

As stated formally in the GDPR.EU site, this is not an absolute right. It has to be requested, it is valid only in certain conditions, and it is not supposed to contribute to the rewriting of history. But the possible misuse of this “right”, namely the de-responsabilization of actions and opinions, the abolishment of biography anchored in due time, and the political hygienization of past social values, is not what we want to discuss here. What we would like to discuss are the nuances in the interpretation and operationalization of this “right to be forgotten”, juxtapositioning it to the ‘right to be remembered, heard and seen’ as a microcosm of the society and a testimony on its own. Afterall, it is possible and desirable to look at longitudinal quantitative data as a storyline of life (Sahrland *et al.*, 2017) and to look for hardship, cries for help, and inequalities in unusual places and data (Nico *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, where possible ‘right to be remembered’ should also apply to migrants and their experience of migration.

How do children and young people address and think about this balance and interdependence between different human and social rights? The Youth Advisory Board to the Coordinate Project’s Meetings provides us insight on how to navigate this grey ethical area. The Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) were constituted in the UK and in Portugal, with young people of 14 to 20 years of age. The meetings were held during 2022, during which it was possible to gather the YAB’s reflections and opinions about issues such as longitudinal studies, data protection, data linkage and the ethical questions surrounding these matters.

Attrition vs. act of care

Attrition is related to the problem of losing participants during longitudinal project because participants become temporarily or indefinitely unreachable. This can be because they lose interest or become unable to do so for other reasons. Losing participants means leaving question marks where answers and codes should have been. Literature informs us that socially vulnerable and/or mobile people are disproportionately more likely to fall into the categories of the “ones left behind” or “left unseen”. If doing no harm to the participants in quantitative and qualitative research is consensual (even though the definition of actually “doing harm” can be debatable)³, going further into the “act of care” is disproportionately used in qualitative research.

We argue that we should “think attrition qualitatively” (Nico *et al.*, 2018) and from a “friendship as method” (Tillman-Healy, 2003) point of view. Tillman-Healy argues that research, especially longitudinal (mostly qualitative) research, should be carried out with the same ethics of friendship. For example, the researchers should solicit fears and concerns, listen closely, respond compassionately, use such exchanges to refine the study and direct its implications, and treat the participants with respect. This is mainly during the face-to-face interactions and interview, but even after, one should: honour their stories and try to use the stories for human and fair purposes. This implies a sustained immersion in the participants’ lives and offering a processual and longitudinal approach. Of course, this seems more suitable to qualitative research, and applying this to quantitative data requires a more attentive approach to movements, oscillations, red flags, and gaps in the collection of data. If the sample and the

³ For instance, is promoting reflexivity on sensitive topics doing harm?

results are socially structured, so should the follow-up to the participants be. This shift in the approach can turn concerns with “attrition” with concerns with “people”.

These commitments to each other’s role in the process of research was enhanced by the YABs, that also underlined the fact that this commitment is a two-way street. Young people from one of the YABs feel that longitudinal studies are of great interest because their findings can potentially help people in the future. That said, they find these types of studies to be very demanding and complex and understand the difficulty in keeping the participants engaged throughout the years. They feel that people change over time so they can lose interest and enthusiasm and that children and young people are groups where this can easily happen because of the rapid changes in their lives and the related uncertainty of life. Although in terms of consent and renewing consent in each wave of the study, they express unanimously that consent is a right that must be confirmed during the time of the project to guarantee that people want to continue participating (the so called in ethnography renegotiation of entrée), they also hesitate about the absolute right to withdraw consent. They feel that people have the right to change their minds about participating and by doing so, they should have the right to withdraw consent, but they understand it’s complicated in terms of the study itself to deal with these setbacks. This coincidentally relates to the GDPR regulation that elaborates on the idea of the research validity consequences of the “right to be forgotten”.

Young people have underlined that the research team and the participants should nurture a relationship where information and trust flow to prevent participants from quitting. Transparency and trust act as an antidote to withdrawing consent and to follow out of the survey. Caring about the participants, caring about the results, caring about who will benefit from them. A multidimensional act of care can prevent low participation and engagement in a survey. Furthermore, each participant in a survey can perform, as an interview, the “confessional effect” mentioned by Brückner and Mayer (1998), in which the participants find a safe space in the context of a research to tell and denounce harsh or vulnerable situations in their lives. This can be especially useful for children and young people suffering from lack of social integration, war trauma, human trafficking, and mobility issues.

In order to ensure research integrity, quality, and trust, university and research institution Ethics committees oversee and carefully examine each research projects and ensure that appropriate ethical and governance guidelines have been followed. Establishing trust between the research project and attendees is also important because participants’ trust in the research may limit their possibility of dropping out of the study. Ethics committees often emphasize the importance of the study information letters and informed consent sent to the study participants, which also increases trust in the research project. Giving a consent to participate expresses trust from the part of the respondent in the research project, however, in most cases participants pay little or no attention on the information letter and simply assumes that research projects have already been carefully evaluated by the Ethical committees of the research institutions (implying high trust in them) (see also Lessof, 2009). In addition to the formal documents, the role of interviewers has a major role in eliciting participants’ trust in the research integrity. Thus, support and training of the interviewers before and during the project is of high importance (Lessof, 2009). A basic model of trust in survey procedures is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. A basic model of trust in survey procedures (based on the conceptual model presented in Lessof, 2009)

Anonymization vs. humanization

The nurture of a relationship of transparency and trust between participants and researchers is clear during real time and face-to-face interactions, but it is mostly possible through humanization not only of the participants but also of the researchers. The absolute need to protect the data of the individual from others and thus maintain its confidentiality, anonymisation and pseudonymisation can, when taken to an extreme, contribute to de-humanizing the relationship and the individuals involved. Anonymization consists of re-classifying information that can lead to the identification of each participant. This can be done by removing direct identifiers (address, national insurance number, name, address, etc.) and recoding key variables (such as gender age, region and occupation) that when combined could make participants identifiable. There are also sensitive variables, that can be subject to legal or medical issues, for instance. Although less frequent in surveys, there is also sensitive data in terms or intimacy, biographical crisis, abuse or other traumatic experiences. Giving voice to these experiences is not necessarily shedding light on the individuals that have experienced them (Strecht *et al.*, 2023).

If it is true “people” have the right to be forgotten, it may also be equally true that their stories have the “right to be remembered”. One of the motivations of participating in research is to join others while a story of a generation is told. There are many phases of a research where the complete anonymization of the participants stories can be demoralising their whole experience of being heard and seen.

Privacy vs. human rights

The protection of privacy is not an unconditional right. A personal and very private experience may not be subject to the privacy principle, in law, life or research. A longitudinal survey is as an interaction in slow and long motion. It is a fact that sensitive research is often connected to qualitative research, but quantitative research can have a human-rights approach as well. This can consist in the questions asked, or inferred in the answers given: abuse, poverty, arranged marriage, political persecution, forced migration, unsafe migration, human trafficking, the list is immense. A survey can completely or partially have access to information that, even if does not prove or confirm, can at least raise a concern with the

child's wellbeing. In such instances, where researchers are concerned about the welfare of participants, it will be necessary for researchers to identify the relevant authorities and alert them to the risk.

In the discussions with young people in the YAB meetings, it was clear that the protection of the child's right is above and beyond any research plan or scientific agenda. YAB members advise researchers to "listen" – or in the case of quantitative surveys, to "see" - carefully and encourage the child to share any issue of concern. After assessing the risk/harm involved in what the child is sharing, even when she/he isn't aware of the seriousness of the matter, researchers should facilitate the child's access to the person/people who can help her/him formally. The child should be empowered for being able to disclose the issue of concern, while researchers should reassure the child that it's not her/his responsibility.

Privacy should not be compliance to violent or dangerous situations, or human rights violations. Or an excuse for a bystander-type research.

Concluding notes: humanizing quantitative longitudinal research

The future research ethical agenda and mission implies an attentive connection to an ever- changing society. In spite of challenges such as the volatile perception of the value of research and science, the diminishing scientific public funding, dysfunctional national scientific systems, social researchers are not short of options when it comes to finding solutions to improve societal development. Research and researchers can do so by following ethical guidelines and advice such as doing no harm, enhancing reciprocity and honouring the stories told, the answers given and the time offered by the participants of a study. This generosity of time is even more valuable when it is longitudinal and occupies a significant section of a life span.

Research funding is usually circumscribed. To a country, to an area, to an institution. The field work may have to reflect these frontiers, and often does. But when one is dealing with wellbeing and with children with wide open possibilities of residential and other trajectories, these frontiers should be challenged. Not only, perhaps not mainly, for scientific sake, of grasping global processes, but also for humanistic purposes. Trying to avoid young people from dropping out of a survey because they are mobile (likely because of economic, demographic and/or security reasons) or to be excluded from a survey based on the fact they are not European-born should be a basic ethical research responsibility. Indeed, the inclusion of migrants and their trajectories and experiences in longitudinal studies should be seen as an important social and scientific objective. It is possible that this will become more urgent in the future as political and global events create new drivers of migration within and beyond Europe.

This is even more relevant if we take into account the crises outside the EU and how migration has taken on a major role in recent European politics. Facing population ageing combined with low birth rates and labour force shortages, governments struggle to manage reception and integration measures for migrants and managing public opinion. The wars and conflicts in Europe, at the frontiers of the European Union as it stands today, have to be taken into account, and including, in the EU but also in the surveys developed on its behalf, participants from these territories is an ethical issue.

The research endeavour of a project such as a pan-European longitudinal survey about wellbeing implies anticipating both the procedural and the ethical questions raised by this social occurrence. The first thought is that it is very important to acknowledge the impact of migration in terms of people's objective and subjective wellbeing thus necessary to implement tailored strategies to avoid their attrition from the study. At the same time, researchers must guarantee that these mobility movements are respected and protected in terms of privacy.

These apparently conflicting ideas set the tone for this deliverable. How can longitudinal research cope with following participants throughout their migration paths while staying GDPR compliant? How can it conciliate concerns with privacy in a human rights approach; anonymization practices in a humanistic fashion, attrition-avoidance concerns with the act of longitudinally care?

Research should always privilege the common good and heighten scientific knowledge. Researchers have the freedom to choose which social issues to study and design methods to address them, while engaging with recognised ethical principles and practices. Often, this "only" means following a legalist stance which accounts for checking items like consent forms, data collection, protection and storage protocols, anonymization processes, among many other ethical principles disseminated by several research infrastructure guidelines and regulated by the GDPR.

We argue that research in order to keep pace with a dynamic and ever evolving social reality that raises new questions and concerns, should combine these ethical practices with a more situational ethical approach, sensitive to a case-by-case humanistic analysis and decision making. The bridging between these different and apparently irreconcilable paradigms is fundamental in a long-term research project.

GDPR favours research in exchange for appropriate safeguards. Some argue that this regulation has excessively limited the research range of action, allowing for a mistrustful environment to settle which is damaging for scientific purposes. Complying with the GDPR requirements is only the start in respecting and protecting the participants' fundamental (human) rights.

Longitudinal surveys, which cover several countries within a continent, need to include migrants and mobile citizens. Not only because, as said, it is a means to assess particular wellbeing issues but also as a way to humanize the unit of analysis and ultimately to stand for human rights protection. Migrants are considered vulnerable people and so, legitimate subjects of special safeguards. Adding to this, it is important that ethical conduct assumes a context-oriented approach that recognizes the participants' potential and positions and is willing to challenge for instance, the interpretation and application of the "right to be forgotten" versus the "right to be remembered".

In general, the best practices for this type of studies indicate that renewing consent at each wave – position that is supported by the Young Advisory Board members – is indicated to encompass change, either in participants themselves or in the basis for consent. Regarding migration, researchers must be alert when people come into a study country and provide means to integrate them into the sample.

Attrition can pose a great risk to the study. This is particularly relevant in young people moving out from their family's house or migrants that move within a country or out of it. To avoid attrition from jeopardizing the study validity, both in terms of meaning and representation, research design must

calculate a larger sample to accommodate potential dropouts. Tracing respondents in their mobilities can weigh on researchers' workload as well as it can raise ethical questions. Sharing participants' information between national survey teams would need their consent, for instance.

In this paper, we argue that carrying out a quantitative longitudinal study based on humanistic methods based on proximity and care might be an effective way to minimize attrition. This position is also endorsed by Youth Advisory Board members who advise for transparent and trustful research relations to be nurtured. Humanizing respondents, favouring their stories rather than anonymising their experiences follows the same research motto. The same approach should apply to participants' sensitive matters. Whether it is in the questions asked, the answers given or later, when analysing the data sets, researchers can input a preventive and human rights driven attention into the study.

When confronted with scenarios that mimic these ethical dilemmas, young people who were consulted prioritize the wellbeing of the child. They assume the role of the researcher is of a potential moderator of sensitive situations, where the child or minor might be at risk. In these cases, the participants advise the researchers to overcome any scientific agendas and perform the important role of facilitation the contact with information, services, institutions or people that are competent to help. Vulnerability is not a variable. Researchers must not follow a detached bystander-approach. Participants can tell the difference, and that will make a difference.

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2 Administrative data linkage

Ethics, Data Linkage, and Children in Europe

Introduction

In many European countries it is now routine for social survey data to be combined with administrative data. The primary reason for doing so is to enhance research by allowing users to supplement the content of social surveys with administrative data held by national statistics authorities and other organisations. This can allow researchers to answer questions beyond the scope of the original survey by incorporating new information. Supplementing survey data in this way can also improve more technical aspects of a survey, such as adjusting for non-response bias and designing sampling frames (Calderwood and Lessof, 2009). It can also reduce the burden on respondents of completing long social surveys, which can improve survey and item response (Michaud et al., 1995). For longitudinal surveys administrative data can be used to fill in gaps between waves and potentially to link to measures before the survey began, after it ended or respondents dropped out (Peycheva et al., 2021). This could be particularly important for cohort studies where the typical gap between sweeps might be a number of years. For example, in the UK the ability to link the Next Steps cohort study or the Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) to educational records using the National Pupil Database provides researchers with an invaluable source of detailed data that would not be available in a standard survey.

Nevertheless, linking survey data to administrative records raises important ethical questions particularly when the information collected concerns children. Key among these is the issue of informed consent (Jäckle et al., 2021). That is, it is generally accepted that adults are able to consent to data collection and agree to their data being used in particular ways. However, very young children are not able to provide consent and it is unclear at what point consent can be provided by children and young people. Laws surrounding this also differ between countries which adds a further challenge to cross-national research. Longitudinal studies may be affected by changes in legal frameworks over time. For example, the introduction of GDPR in the European Union in 2018 affected the way which existing studies processed data (Christen et al., 2020). Going beyond these concerns there are also important questions to be asked about the way in which consent to link data is provided and maintained. This is a particularly important question when the subjects of the research are young children whose parents will need to consent on their behalf, but who may eventually be in a position to provide consent themselves during the lifespan of the study.

To some extent these issues fall within the broader discussions around data privacy that are occurring as societies adjust to mass data collection by both public and private organisations. National and cross-national bodies have been seeking to address these issues. For example, the EU adopted the far-reaching General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) in 2018 (EU, 2018). The GDPR enshrines the rights of privacy and data protection of individuals within the EU and European Economic Area (EEA). This has a number of implications for how research is conducted (Vukovic et al., 2022): it has been found to act as an enabling mechanism in terms of increasing respondents confidence that their data will be used

appropriately, facilitating the sharing of anonymised data, and in promoting increased transparency. However, the regulation was not adopted evenly between, and within, those countries affected by it which has led to different interpretations about what is, and is not, permissible. Consequently, certain barriers to research cooperation have been raised.

All research within the EU and EEA must comply with the GDPR. This is especially important when that data relates to young people who are considered to be part of a vulnerable group under GDPR, which attaches extra protections to the handling of their data. However, data collected for scientific and policy making purposes has a number of special features which it is important to reflect on. A key consideration should be the fact that participants in social surveys do not benefit directly from doing so. Rather they are assured that taking part will have general benefits, such as improving public policy or increasing scientific understanding of a given issue. As such it is incumbent on researchers to ensure that appropriate study protocols are developed to ensure that respondents understand, and consent to, what may happen with the data that they provide. Indeed, one purpose of this paper is to reflect on what young people understand about the process of survey and administrative data linkage and how they perceive the risks and benefits. A key feature of the work described here involves engaging young people in the process as early as possible. A prior, related project, known as MYWeb, involved young people to reflect on what wellbeing meant to them and to consider how best to conduct the study (Pollock et al., 2018). In this phase of the project we have sought to engage groups of young people to consider the ethical and practical dimensions of being involved in a cohort study from an early age.

Gaining informed consent can also have practical benefits. In a discussion of the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC), which included children born in the then county of Avon, UK, in 1991 and 1992, Birmingham (2018) notes that a failure to gain appropriate consent at the time of the study caused a significant amount of extra work on the part of the ethics committee, researchers, and participants at later stages. That is, if issues around ethics had been addressed at the beginning of the study, from planning what would have been required to gaining informed consent during the survey phase, the process would have been much easier to manage. There is also a more general point that poor practice on the part of researchers may have an impact on the propensity of individuals who may have initially consented to participate in a study to continue to do so. Elsewhere Nico et al. (2018) demonstrate that involving young people can have a positive impact on recruitment and attrition for example.

In the next section we will discuss in greater detail why linking data can be beneficial, the ethical concerns that it can raise, and the particular concerns for children and young people. Following this we will discuss the findings from our Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) undertaken as part of the COhort cOmmunity Research and Development Infrastructure Network (COORDINATE) project.

Administrative Data Linkage, Ethical Research, and Children

The process of linking survey and administrative data

Administrative data is not collected with the primary aim of using it for social research. Rather, it is routinely collected by governments, national statistical agencies, and associated organisations, for the purposes of record-keeping as part of the normal operation of the organisation (Dibben et al., 2015).

The primary use of the data may be to monitor health, educational, or other social outcomes. However, administrative data can provide a rich source of information to inform studies about a wide range of outcomes of interest to social scientists and policy makers. In the present discussion we are concerned with administrative data that is linked to social survey data, and the ethical implications of doing so. It is worth noting that administrative data does not need to be linked to social survey data in order to be of value. Indeed, some of the most promising uses of administrative data come from linking different administrative datasets to one another (Harron et al., 2017). This can provide a valuable source of data using whole populations. In addition, new longitudinal data sources can be created allowing researchers to study the effects of policy over time (Connelly et al., 2016; Pattaro et al., 2020; Picot and Piraino, 2013). Data linkage can also be used to address technical issues relating to sample design (Smith, 2011), attrition, and item non-response.

When data has been collected as part of a social survey it is often possible to link it to administrative data. For much of this discussion we are concerned with the ethics of gaining informed consent and how this relates to the way informed consent is achieved for children and young people. However, it is important to discuss the ways in which data is linked as this will help explain why informed consent is important due to some of the risks involved in the process. The linkage may be done at either the individual or aggregate level. Individual level linkage is concerned with matching survey response data with individual administrative records. Aggregate data linkage often involves matching geographical units to understand the social environment within which people live. It is very common to match local deprivation levels onto social survey data. For example Knies and Kumari (2022) assess the relationship between multimorbidity and the different dimensions of the Index of Multiple Deprivation, a measure of area deprivation, in England and Wales.

Individual level data linkage involves matching survey responses to person level information held by the state. This can allow researchers to explore information not included in the original survey and to examine events that happen after the original survey took place. One form of data linkage that is particularly relevant for young people is linking to educational records. For instance, the National Pupil Database (NPD) in the UK allows researchers to link both pupil level and school level information which can allow researchers to include non-biased educational outcome information and to understand the context within which educational outcomes occurred, in their research (see Jay et al., (2019) for a comprehensive discussion of the NPD). Elsewhere the Nordic registry data, available in Denmark, Finland, Norway, and Sweden offer a unique opportunity to link survey data to a wide range of social phenomena from health, education, local area, and more for almost the total population of these countries (Smith Jervelund and De Montgomery, 2020). This allows researchers, with the correct identifier to link survey data for any individual in those countries to the registry. Many other countries throughout Europe have, or are developing, a way for researchers to access administrative data.

In both instances this linkage is likely to involve the use of information that is not available in data that is released to the research community. Aggregate data can be linked at any available level geography if an appropriate geographic identifier is available. For face-to-face surveys this would typically be an address. This information can be mapped onto administrative data and used to assess the impact of contextual factors. Typically, this increases the risk of identification of people included in the survey, particularly if geographic identifiers themselves are made available to researchers. This is because when combined with other information included in a survey, such as family size and the ages of household

members it may be possible to identify specific families and household members, at a sufficiently low geographical level.

When data is linked at the individual level a number of different approaches can be taken (see Schnell, 2014). The most accurate and straightforward, known as *exact* or *direct* data matching, is to collect a unique ID number that is available in the administrative data that is to be linked to. The data can then be straightforwardly matched. The second, known as *probabilistic* matching, occurs when this kind of ID variable is not available or where there is error in the ID number matching. This approach takes a common set of variables available in the survey and administrative data and calculates whether there is a match based on a given threshold. As with the linking of aggregate data, ethical issues arise due to the increased risk that the data will be disclosive. This is because adding additional, possibly more finely grained data, increases the chance that identifying features of an individual might be present in the data. A second, related but additional, concern relates to the possibility that the data which is being linked to might contain much more sensitive information than that collected in the survey. For instance detailed health or education data might contain information that survey respondents might have been uncomfortable about disclosing.

In practice it may not be possible to guarantee that linked data will be completely anonymised (Ohm, 2010). Rather, and as Dibben et al (2015) discuss, it is necessary to create an environment where data is functionally anonymous. This is done through the development of governance and security structures that condition the behaviour of researchers and enforces strict rules about how researchers access potentially disclosive data. This data environment will typically be guided by strict rules governing the procedures used to access the data. The stricter these are the more protected both data subjects and researchers are (the latter because it makes accidental disclosure much more difficult). A strict application process and ethics procedure should ensure that the research is in the public interest and meets appropriate standards of rigour. There is a need to 'shape' safe behaviour through training and potential sanctions. Secure and safe environments will need to be used to control where and how the data is accessed. Taken together. And perhaps with further controls where necessary such an environment can render data effectively anonymous.

Ethics, children, and data linkage

Ethical issues are raised when linking survey and administrative data, particularly around consent. In some instances, there may be specific legal requirements that seek to ensure consent is granted before data linkages are made. This is a requirement under GDPR. Even in the absence of specific legal requirements, however, it is good practice to always gain consent before linking data. It is worth noting that some research has found that participants were open to the idea of data linkage without consent provided data was first anonymised (Xafis, 2015). As was noted above a failure to gain consent to undertake data linkages can result in significant ethical problems at a later stage of research. This might mean time needs to be spent working with ethics panels to determine where and when a data linkage is appropriate and may lead to the need to seek consent after the initial survey, or in the case of panel surveys at a later wave. Each of these would be likely to lead to substantially more time spent, and delays, than if appropriate consent is sought at the beginning of the study.

These issues become significantly more complicated when the focus of the social survey is on children. Primarily this is because young children cannot give consent themselves and it is therefore necessary to obtain parental consent. In this case of a cross-sectional survey this may cause no further problems. However, in the case of longitudinal research where the child/parents may be resurveyed many times over the course of their lives it will be necessary to re-obtain consent when the child has reached a level of maturity that would allow them to provide it. As Lessof (2009) notes there are a number of ethical questions that arise which relate specifically to longitudinal studies: is it sufficient to gain consent once or should respondents be asked to provide consent at each new survey wave? How long does consent last? Is consent to link data revoked if a participant leaves the study or can new data continue to be linked? Each of these questions apply to studies of which follow children over the life course and can be further caveated by the question of the age at which children themselves can consent to participation. It also raises the question of whether children can revoke consent that had previously been given by a parent.

These can be difficult questions. There is a risk that if a substantial proportion of respondents refuse to give consent to data linkage that the linkage itself would no longer be meaningful or be heavily biased. This is a concern as a substantial amount of scientific and policy value can be gained from undertaking data linkage. It is incumbent upon researchers to maximise the value of these studies given the high cost of such surveys which are generally funded by the public. Thus, researchers need to balance the ethical, and legal, requirements that they have to participants with a broader focus on the need to create scientifically sound sources of evidence that can in turn form a strong evidence base for policy makers.

There is an increasing body of work focused on who provides consent for data linkage (Sala et al., 2012), mechanisms for increasing consent (Jäckle et al., 2022; Sala et al., 2014), and that linking to different kinds of data can result in different rates of consent (Edwards and Biddle, 2021). These are important questions and it is clear that factors such as differential response rates among can affect the quality of research outputs and may lead to underrepresentation of vulnerable groups in the linked data. This is a point noted by Baghani (2016) in one of the few such studies which has focused on the ways in which parents and carers provide consent for their children. It was noted that mothers were less likely to provide consent for their children than themselves and were more likely to consent to data linkage to educational records than health records. It is also notable that there were ethnic differences in consent to link data with those from a minority ethnic background being less likely to do so. It has been found the way in which multiple requests for consent are ordered can have an impact, although the precise way in which this works has not been established (Walzenbach et al., 2022).

There have been few studies which have sought to explicitly seek to ask children and young people about their views of data linkage. A notable example is Audrey et al., (2016) who conducted a qualitative study of members of the ALSPAC study about their views concerning data linkage. A key finding of this study suggested that even among a group of participants who had been engaged in a research study for a number of years it was difficult to explain the details of what consent meant across a range of scenarios, with participants tending to default to the assumption that consent means 'asking' whether or not their data could be used even when other types of consent had been explained.

In the remainder of this paper we explain the approach to the YABs that we took for the purposes of this study. We then discuss the findings from these and relate them back to some of the key ethical issues highlighted above.

The Youth Advisory Boards

Composition and methods

As part of the COORDINATE project a series of Youth Advisory Boards were convened to inform our approach to the study and to include the voices of younger people from as early a stage as possible. This was the second Youth Advisory Board (YAB) that this group had participated in. The advisory board in Portugal was asked to consider administrative data linkage and related ethical issues. It was composed of 3 young people between the ages of 17 and 20 and was a mixed group. The discussion followed a script which focused on different aspects of participating in longitudinal studies with a particular focus on data protection, data linkage, and the ethical issues involved in these. The Youth Advisory Board (YAB) members were allowed to freely discuss these and encouraged to contribute their own thoughts.

Results

An overarching theme arising from the discussions was that even for topics such as data linkage, which can be both technical and abstract, was that taking a child centric approach is important and feasible. Young people can and did contribute to a discussion of ethical issues surrounding this topic in a meaningful and nuanced way.

After reintroducing the context of the study the discussion first focused on some of the issues of participating in a longitudinal study such as data protection and data linkage. Participants found the former much easier to understand than the latter. Data protection is a topic which young people were already familiar with, especially in relation to their online behaviour, cyber bullying, and human rights on the internet. Thus, they felt comfortable dealing with this issue and felt comfortable sharing their thoughts about it. By contrast it was felt that data linkage was not something they had considered previously. However, they quickly understood the fundamental points and were able to contribute to a discussion of the issues.

There was an agreement that longitudinal studies can be important insofar as they might generate social benefits in the future. However, there was some concern that such studies can be demanding and that it might be difficult to maintain response over many years. A key point raised concerned the notion that people may change in their views and beliefs over time and that this is particularly important point when dealing with children and younger people. As one participant noted:

"I don't think you should ever assume someone's consent. I think it's always ethical to make sure the person is comfortable as they're asking questions about your personal life. Even because what I thought 5 years ago may no longer be what I think today." I. (woman, 17 years old, Secondary)

When addressing data protection and data linkage issues, YAB members have a wide definition for personal data, and they feel that participants should always have the right not to answer to some particular question or set of questions. They advise that researchers should always reinforce that the answers given are anonymous and confidential and that they won't spill over to third parties. Hence, in the specific case of data linkage, YAB members understand that it can be relevant for research purposes but argue that participants should agree and consent that their information will be linked with other databases. There should be a specific consent form to allow for data linkage in each wave of the project. YAB members have strong feelings and are unanimous about the need to give longitudinal and specific consent for this data linkage. As such, it is not a universal or one size fits all consent. Instead, it depends on the age of the individual of the data to be linked and the type of data to be linked *per se*. The key point is that "informed" consent is essential rather than consent in an abstract way.

"Researchers should share a document with detailed information so that people can give a truly informed consent about what data will be linked and what are the rules for this.", A. (woman, 18 years old, Secondary)

"Data linkage may be relevant to the research but the person must give her/his specific consent in order for such data linkage to take place.", T. (man, 20 years old, University student)

While the YAB agreed that for consent is important and should be sought at each stage of the study they were more ambiguous about being able to withdraw consent retroactively. They were sympathetic to the notion that doing so might damage the study noting that:

"I think the participants have a moral commitment to the researchers and to the study" A. (woman, 18 years old, Secondary)

"I think people should always have the right to say that after all, no, I don't want to. (...) But it's conflicting because I'm jeopardising the researchers' work and the time they put into this study." I. (woman, 17 years old, Secondary)

It was felt that allowing people to withdraw from a study within a given timeframe would help alleviate some of the ethical concerns raised would help balance the rights of participants to withdraw consent without risking the overall aims of the study. However, YAB members emphasised that the best way to ensure that young people would continue engagement in a longitudinal study would be to foster a relationship of openness and trust between the research team and participants. This will allow participants to feel that they have a shared sense of purpose with the research team.

These concerns have clear implications for data linkage and it is interesting to consider the discussion that the YAB had on this topic with respect to them. While they did feel that data linkage could be an important research tool it is notable that members of the YAB felt more uncomfortable about the prospect of data linkage than they did in participating in a longitudinal study. This notion of transparency concerns not only the fact that the data is shared but also with *whom* the data is shared. The data linkage was a subject which may YAB members feel uncomfortable and suspicious, because they fear that there could be abusive access to personal data beyond the project's purposes. The combination of what data shared, its purposes and who is going to access it, is key for the young people consulted. One participant stated that:

“I think I would be a little scared by the idea of data linkage, because there is a number of people who have access to some of my personal information.”, A. (woman, 18 years old, Secondary)

A view which came across very strongly was that separate consent forms should be provided for participation in a longitudinal study and for linking data, and that this should be provided at each new wave of the study. They also felt that explaining data linkage, as well as research procedures more generally, is an important aspect of the study that should occur even for young children. It was suggested that detailed information should be provided where appropriate and that materials for younger people and children should be developed to help them understand what the data linking procedure would look like. It was also felt that in doing so participants in a longitudinal study which includes data linkage would be more likely to remain engaged in the future. Again, trust is engendered by this transparency. The only way they would feel more confident is by being talked through by researchers with whom they (should) have a trustful relationship. One of the young members put it very clearly:

“I think researchers should explain everything, mainly to prevent any future regrets. The more aware I am at this moment, no matter how young I am, the less regretful I will be in the future and the less I will want to take back what I said.”, T. (man, 20 years old, University student)

It was felt that consent should always be asked for, irrespective of age. YAB members feel it is important to explain data linkage or any other research procedure to the participants no matter their age and that researchers should adapt discourse to meet the child or teenager understanding. In the case of children, researchers should try to bring examples that correspond to the child’s references, such as cartoons or toys and use that to compare and explain things that are abstract.

“Researchers can use things from the cartoons... they can make associations to things the child knows to try to explain, to make the child understand.”, A. (woman, 18 years old, Secondary)

Despite the specifics of the addressed issues, YAB members felt strongly that a transparent and trustful research relationship and a shared sense of purpose of the research are the keys for success in longitudinal studies in spite of the various challenges that data protection or data linkage can pose.

The YAB was then asked to consider a scenario in which they were asked:

Scenario: You are taking part in a research study about wellbeing, researchers would like to link your answers to your educational records as well as health records. To do this they will contact [the education department] and the [health service]. Researchers will send them your data such as your Name, DOB, Address, Gender, Ethnicity [health number], and ask both organisations to return information that they hold about you. Before returning your data the [health service] and [education department] will remove identifying info such as your names and give you a unique ID so that your information remains private. Would you permit researchers to do this? If yes? why? and if not, why? How do you feel about that?

Given this scenario, in which the question has been made much more specific, YAB members were more receptive to the idea of linking data to administrative records. They felt that they would consent if they understood that the linkage had a legitimate purpose and if anonymisation and confidentiality could be guaranteed. It was also noted that understanding that having access to this kind of data would only

occur when necessary was important. That is, having a clearly defined set of rules that would allow access to the information was felt to be very important when seeking consent to link data:

“I think it depends on the study in question because there are certain studies where it is important to know this information from the participants. If I thought it contributed to the study, I don't see why not. On the other hand, if I didn't understand why they want to know this information, I wouldn't agree.”, A. (woman, 18 years old, Secondary)

Finally, in the discussion of this scenario it was again emphasised that a closeness to the researchers would be an important aspect of providing consent. The importance of being able to ensure privacy and confidentiality was also reemphasised:

“I also think that in this case I would accept it if I had that closeness to the researchers and also because confidentiality and the existence of a unique identifier instead of the name are guaranteed. I would be more sure that if there was, for example, a computer attack, my information would not end up in other hands or because they wouldn't know it was me.”, T. (man, 20 years old, University student)

Discussion

The YAB identified many of the key issues concerns that have been raised in the literature previously. To some extent the concerns raised by the study participants are easily, or already, addressed. As has been discussed strict rules in the form of GDPR exist within European countries which provide a clear legal framework around which data can be collected and held. It is also increasingly accepted that for most types of data processing activities specific permission is required and this is increasingly seen as best practice in many settings. Young people were able to contribute in a meaningful way to discussions around data linkage and consent to the use of their data more generally.

Consent to both collect data, and to perform a linkage, was considered to be of high importance to the YAB. Moreover, engaging children and young people in a discussion of the issues related what will happen, irrespective of their age was felt to be important. The specific age at which children or young people are required to provide consent differs across Europe (Macenaite and Kosta, 2017). However, for the purposes of a general longitudinal survey asking children and young people, as well as their parents for consent to engage in data collection and processing is unlikely to present major difficulties. Advice from the YABs to prepare child and young person specific materials, appropriate to age, is well considered and an important aspect of the approach that the COORDINATE project and wider the GUIDE project is taking. That is, where possible children and young people will receive documentation explaining what is being collected and what will be done with the data after it has been collected.

It is hoped that the approach will also help in addressing the point which ran throughout much of the discussion that YAB members felt that fostering an environment of trust and transparency with young people would be the best way to achieve consent and alleviate any concerns that people might have. This fits well with other findings which suggest that factors such as interviewer-respondent rapport can be an important factor in establishing consent (Al Baghal, 2016). Clearly the practicalities of generating a shared sense of purpose between researchers and respondents can be difficult. In large scale survey

based research when the interviewing will be undertaken by professional research agencies. It has been shown that from an ensuring where possible that face-to-face surveys generate higher consent for data linkage requests (Thornby et al., 2018). Respondents having trust in the research team was also emphasised and has been shown to be an important factor when establishing and maintaining consent. In their discussion of qualitative research undertaken into the reasons for consent to link data, as part of the Understanding Society study, Jäckle et al., (2021) suggest that this is one of the key heuristics that respondents rely on when providing consent.

Conclusion

Data linkage between survey data and administrative records will continue to increase in popularity as researchers and policy makers become increasingly aware of the benefits of doing so. It will become increasingly important therefore for researchers to ensure that they have properly engaged in a process of gaining informed consent when they wish to do so. Indeed, the young people in the YABs suggest that consent to data linkage should be an integral part of the data collection process. This group suggested that being clear and open about the reasons for doing so, as well as in the research process more generally, would help children and young people to feel empowered and valued by researchers. Throughout it was emphasised that establishing trust and rapport between the researchers and young people would be helpful for the research overall. The use of age-appropriate materials for explaining what data linkage is was strongly encouraged by the YABs and will continue to be pursued by the project. Overall, the discussion above reinforces our view that children should be involved in the design of research as was argued. Taking such a child centric-approach, it is argued, should help develop and then reinforce the notion that participants in the study are working together with researchers.

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3 Data Access

What do young people think about their rights to access survey data?⁴

As part of our work on ethics and young people a series of Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) have been held in which young people have had the opportunity to express their views about a range of topics related to the COORDINATE and GUIDE projects. In one of these sessions, we asked them to consider what 'Access to Data' might mean for children and young people. In particular we were interested in exploring their thoughts on the notion that there is a balance to be struck between the 'right to be forgotten'(EU, 2018a) established by formal and legal guidelines on how to handle personal data; and the 'the right to be remembered' (Correia, Nico and Alves, 2019) as a relational and situational ethical principle, related to the good practice of doing no harm and enhancing reciprocity between researcher and participants. Reaching this balance is one of the fundamental challenges in protecting and respecting the participant and the participant's data.

The right to be remembered is related to the right of the participating children to be part of the research community and to feel as though their contributions are valuable and valued. Participating in a survey also means that once data has been collected it provides valuable information about groups of children with shared characteristics, allowing researchers and policy makers to understand the experiences and needs of these groups. Acknowledging this is remembering and honouring their stories and answers. As such, allowing data to be deleted, to be forgotten, without consideration of the scientific demerits of doing so can bias the data and analysis, especially if those deletions are concentrated among specific sub-groups, most likely more vulnerable. Ultimately, deleting data might result in the loss of the dataset as a viable scientific resource, due to the exclusion of particular groups of young people. There is a risk that not being statistically included might result in further social exclusion of the most at risk groups.

Discussing consent and its withdrawal is one of the ways in which we can address this dilemma. YAB members expressed the view that consent should be able to be withdrawn at any time while being aware that broader obligations to the study exist may impinge on this right:

"Given that it's a very private information about my life, I think people should always have the right to say that after all, no, I don't want to. (...) But it's conflicting because I'm jeopardising the researchers' work and the time they put into this study. ", I. I. (woman, 17 years old, Secondary)

These concerns can be addressed under the GDPR. GDPR relates to the protection of personal data and protection of the individuals. It defines personal data as 'information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person' (EU, 2018b). Broadly speaking, individuals have rights to access, rectify, and erase their personal data. Under this definition all data remains personal until it has been fully anonymised. This means that study participant rights relate to their *personal* data and, in most instances, a request to erase data would mean the anonymization of the of the study data for that

⁴ To be used as a blogpost with hyperlinks added

participant (i.e. the deletion of all personal identifying information). Given the open nature of most academic surveys, information about the kind of data that has been collected should be freely available. Individuals also have the right to access their personal information.

When data is collected appropriately, participants provide their informed consent, and the data is processed on the correct legal basis, data can therefore be retained when it is fully anonymized (Hadziselimovic et al. 2017.). Participants of a study should, and do, have the right to have their personal data deleted, but they do not have the right, in most cases, to have all the data that they have provided deleted. The principle underlying this is that once any identifying information has been destroyed the data can no longer be traced back to an individual.

However, throughout this discussion there is a tension between what is legally considered personal data and what the YAB considered to be personal information. Some members had a very broad definition of what they considered to be personal data and were concerned about it being misused:

“All data that can be used against us by other people without our consent. Data that can be used to practice some form of discrimination. Practically everything we say, in these contexts, is personal data”, T. (man, 20 years old, University student)

Given this tension between what researchers and participants understand by the term personal data it is incumbent upon the research team to ensure that participants have a proper understanding of what rights they do, and do not, have. These can be difficult concepts for adults to understand (Singer 2003) and COORDINATE is currently in the process of developing and testing materials that will be appropriate for use with children, in conjunction with parental consent forms.

Indeed, a special characteristic of a cohort study involving young children is that it must necessarily be parents, rather than the children themselves, that provided the initial consent to participate. This is necessary for both practical and legal reasons. The same rules concerning access and deletion apply to data collected for children. This means that data collected about a group of people who were unable to consent at the time, would be retained, even if they later wished to withdraw from the study. Under GDPR, parental consent to collect data is sufficient up until the age of 16. However, countries can specify that consent can be lower than this with a minimum age of 13. There is therefore variation in the age at which consent must be sought from children to process their data.

COORDINATE strongly believes that children should feel empowered and engaged in the research process from an early stage. Indeed, this relates back to the first point above when a ‘right to be remembered’ was discussed: that is the importance of involving and engaging children as early as possible as active participants in the research process. One way we can do this is actively seeking their consent even if it isn’t legally necessary to do so. YAB members also emphasised this point and suggested that good communication with children and young people should be a key component of the study:

“While participating in a study, if I see that the purposes of the study at some point do not please me and I do not like how the work is being carried out, I will not want to participate anymore.”, A. (woman, 18 years old, Secondary)

The YABs will continue to be an essential component of the work of the COORDINATE project. The discussion above highlights how they have informed and will continue to inform the thinking of the project around issues of data access and consent to participate. They help emphasise that young people wish to be viewed as active participants when they are involved in survey research. It also emphasises the challenge and importance of ensuring that children and young people are fully informed about the process that they are being asked to consent to.

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